

FAST & SPECIFIC DETECTION OF MICRO AND NANO PLASTIC BY FLOWTHROUGH PLASMONIC SENSING

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Project abstract:

The overall objective is to develop the first reliable technology to reproducibly and specifically identify and quantify individual nanoplastic particles. It will then be used, in collaboration with end-users, to accumulate data for various water, beverage and food samples, adding it to a virtually empty current database due to a lack of suitable techniques. To do so the ESR will develop, according to the size of the plastic particles studied, metallic porous membranes of various thicknesses and pore sizes using various microfabrication techniques. Thereafter a polarimetry setup, with a 45 degree incident angle to the normal of the membrane surface, similar to that used in FP7 Positive, will be used to measure both changes in the birefringence of the membrane and its SERS signals as micro and nanoplastic bind to the pore walls for their specific quantification.

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FAST & SPECIFIC DETECTION OF MICRO AND NANO PLASTIC BY FLOWTHROUGH PLASMONIC SENSING - INITIAL DMP

1. DATA SUMMARY

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

Specify the origin of the data

State the expected size of the data (if known)

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The project aims to develop a novel method for detection of micro and nano plastics by flow through plasmonics to enable successful detection and identification of plastics at sub-micron level. The initial data generated will consist of Raman spectra acquired for different plastic types. Later on, the porous membranes will be incorporated into the setup to get angle resolved Raman spectra for different plastic particles entrapped in the membranes. Once this is successfully done, the porous membranes with metallic nano-particles will be used in the setup to get data related to

angle resolved surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) spectra for micro and nano plastic particles. Thus demonstrating successful detection, identification and quantification of micro and (possibly) nano plastic particles. Numerical modelling of angle resolved SERS will also be carried out prior to the experimentation to determine design parameters for successful experiments.

The data will consist of spectroscopic graphs with the extension .opj, COMSOL files with the extension .mph and polarimetric measurements with extension .csv. The data from initial two formats can also be exported in the csv format. The data thus originating from Raman spectroscopy, polarimetry and numerical modelling.

It is too early to give a good idea about the size of the generated data, however at a rough estimate, it is expected that around 50 GB of data will be collected in the project. Existing data will not be used during this project and all the data acquired during the 3 years will be a property of Aston University and European Commission, with Raman spectroscopy being a popular technique the data will be find much use within the scientific community.

Type of data and information related to its storage can be seen in tabular form below:

Type	Volume	Storage/Dissemination	Expiration	Format
Raman Spectra	GB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space Aston Research Data Explorer	NA	.opj
Simulation files	GB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space Aston Research Data Explorer	NA	.mph
Polarimetric Measurements	MB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space Aston Research Data Explorer	NA	.csv
PhD progress reports	MB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space	NA	.pds .docx
Progress Presentations	GB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space	5 years	.ppt
Research Publications	MB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space Journal/Conference Repository ZONODO.org	NA	.pdf .docx
Dissemination Outreach	&GB	Personal Hard Drive BOX space	NA	.mp3 .mp4

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Outline naming conventions used

Outline the approach towards search keyword

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

The discoverability of data will be ensured by storing it in [Aston Research Data Explorer](#) to enable future reuse. Copies of physical items such as CDs, lab books, manuals will be made and stored. It is planned to use persistent identifiers, preferably Digital Object Identifiers. Appropriate scientific keywords associated with the stored data will be linked to the Aston Research Data Explorer thus enabling efficient data search. Conventions, formats etc generally used by Aston University will be used.

Open metadata is a priority to be resolved for next version following community standards where they exist. Metadata uploaded on the server will follow formats specified by Aston University and will contain data description, authors, affiliation, funding body, date of creation and short description.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

Specify how the data will be made available

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

Data will be able to be kept openly available as it will GDPR compliant (e.g. anonymization of personal details from surveys). Data will mostly be in the form of Raman spectra which will be collected in the form of a database. All collected data, associated metadata, documentation and code will be made available at first instance through Aston Research Data Explorer, and then via other platforms where possible to help make data more accessible. All data will be stored in commonly used formats that do not require specially designed software or tools to read/write them.

The snapshot below shows the different research outputs that Aston Research Data Explorer supports:

Research Units 69

Profiles 772

Research Outputs 29570

Datasets 310

Student theses 4722

Activities 2871

More 1021

Unformatted manuscripts (pre-prints) and the peer reviewed manuscripts with corrections (post-prints) will be made freely available following their publication in . Metadata associated with the papers will also be openly available for free access following their publication. All necessary steps will be taken to ensure maximum and free of cost access to the conducted research for future references.

Restrictions on open free access due to commercialization, patent application or IP protection for this project are not envisioned. However, if such a situation arises in future, all relevant data will be protected according to procedures outlined by the MONPLAS consortium.

Aston University provides two categories of open access namely Green Access and Gold Access. The Green Access makes the entire text available free of cost on Aston's research data repository after the embargo period which is generally between 6-24 months. In Gold Open Access the researcher pays Article Processing Charge post which the published article is available as open access immediately via the publisher's website.

2.3 Making data interoperable:

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

As Raman spectroscopy is a well-established technique, the collected data will be of probable interest to many current and future researchers, hence, all the data will be stored in standard formats to ensure interoperability. Open metadata is a priority to be resolved for next version following community standards where they exist. Efforts will be made to store data in standard formats accessible by open source software. Standard vocabulary for all data types present in the data set will be used in order to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and data exchange among research community, universities, funding bodies, research institutes, commercial companies etc. To increase the ease of data search and make stored data easily accessible and interoperable, it will be associated with keywords in the database and be stored with discoverable names having date, technique, principal investigator, affiliation, version number (if applicable), funding body, project, license type etc. Following further research, standards, ontologies and vocabularies related to spectroscopy will be priority for the next version.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Describe data quality assurance processes

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

Creative Common Licenses will be utilized with the minimum restrictions that comply with MONPLAS disclosure protocols to avoid burning of Intellectual Property Right (IPR). The data will be available as open source for everyone through channels generally used by Aston University such as Aston Research Data Explorer. According to Aston's policy the data stored in Aston Research Data Explorer will be available for a minimum of 10 years. Following that, the decision on extending the retention of the data will be made based on the use of the data in the past by the research community. With the permission and help of Aston University steps will be taken to combine storage of Aston Research Data Explorer with ZENODO.org to ensure storage beyond the minimum 10 years offered by Aston University. Care will be taken to make all data including metadata freely available as soon as possible after publication. At the moment need for data embargo is not envisioned Care will be taken to time disclosure of research results intelligently to ensure maximum societal impact. Help and guidance from the MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee will be taken in this matter.

The data produced in the project will be useable by third parties even after the project concludes. All the data collected will be allocated to Creative Commons License to ensure widest reuse possible in the public domain enabling other researchers to reuse and build upon the research without worrying about copyright issues.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

The costs will be covered from the project budget and are part of the Horizon 2020 grant. Estimation of the cost at this stage of the project is not possible, however, it will include at least the setting up and maintenance of a database. Aston University will be responsible for the long term preservation of data in Aston Data Explorer and all the relevant costs for this matter will be covered by Aston University.

As micro and nano plastics are a growing health and environment concern, long term preservation of the collected data will be beneficial. Keeping this in mind, it has been planned to keep the stored data safe for a minimum of 10 years, following this period future decisions about preservation will be made based on the demand and use of the data to date.

The data management responsibility falls upon the principal investigator Aisha Bibi, she, along with the help of her supervisors, Dr. Daniel Hill and Prof. David Webb, and MONPLAS project manager, Ms. Samantha Lees, will ensure that all data and metadata relevant to the project is made FAIR.

4. DATA SECURITY

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Aston University advises the storage of data and metadata on Aston Data Research Explorer which is archived through Arkivum. Arkivum is a UK based leading software company that has expertise in long term data management and digital preservation. It holds a 27001 data security certification and serves their clients by storing and maintaining data in Tier-3 data centers based in the UK. In case of a mishap all the lost data can be easily recovered from Arkivum.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

The only ethical concerns related to the project deliverables identified is that in regard to the disposal of micro and nano plastics post experimentation. For this purpose local environmental regulations and policies will apply and all their necessary protocols will be followed ensuring no environmental concerns arise as a result of the work done during the project.

6. OTHER

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

None at the moment.